

STUDENT ENGAGEMENT, MOTIVATIONAL BELIEFS AND SOCIAL SUPPORT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS: DIFFERENCE IN GENDER AND AGE

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Abstract

The present study is designed to examine the impact of motivational beliefs and social support on student engagement of senior secondary school students. The respondents were students from 3 government senior secondary schools of Amritsar district which included 200 students both male and female selected by Randomly sampling method. Data were collected using Student engagement scale by kamat, Vasudha and falleiro, Sameena (2013), motivational beliefs scale by Singh and Kavita (2019) and social support scale by Dull and Godara (2016). Results found that the Females students have higher student engagement than male adolescent students. Further it was revealed that females students were better in behavioral dimension of students' engagement than males' students. It was found that students of 16 years age group exhibited better student engagement followed by 15 and 14 years of students. Further the present study revealed that students of different age group differ with respect to cognitive and affective domain of student engagement. The present study revealed that males and females students do not differ with respect to motivational beliefs. Further, study found that students of different age group do not differ with respect to motivational beliefs. It was found that the females students perceive higher social support than male students. there was a significant difference found between different dimensions (Family support, teacher support, friends peer support and online support) of social support. so present study revealed that females students have higher family, teacher, friends peer and online support than males students.

Keywords: Student engagement, Motivational beliefs, Social support, Secondary school students.

INTRODUCTION

Students are engaged when they are actively immersed in their task, persevere in the face of difficulties, and show a clear sense of satisfaction in completing it (Schlechty, 2001). Student involvement also includes a “student's willingness, need, desire and compulsion to participate in, and be successful in, the learning process promoting higher level thinking for enduring understanding” (1997, p. 294) (Bomia, Beluzo, Demeester, Elander, Johnson, & Sheldon). Student motivation in a learning environment relates to how much work and concentration a student puts into their studies in order to succeed. Sound student learning depends heavily on motivation and engagement. According to Sternberg (2005), motivation is crucial for academic success since without it, a student may never put up the effort to learn. Motivation is seen as a pre-requisite of and a necessary element for student engagement in learning. Student In addition to being a goal in and of itself, participation in education also serves as a tool for students to achieve sound academic results (Russell, Ainley & Frydenberg, 2005; Ryan & Deci, 2009). When Lin (2012) outlined the connection between student engagement and academic motivation. He viewed the idea of academic drive as a type of discipline that positively or negatively affects a person's behaviours. In addition, academic motivation, In addition to student involvement affected by a person's objectives, prior experiences, cultural context, as well as the teachers' and peers' opinions of the person. According to Middleton and Spanias (1999), motivation is the justification people make for acting in a particular way in a situation. Whether the support received from other people with whom individuals interact is positive or negative affects their motivation (Ersoy-Kart & Guldu 2008; Garavandi et al. 2015).

STUDENT ENGAGEMENT

Students' Engagement is a term used to express a person's improvement and interest in education, which influences their educational achievement and activities (Gallup, 2013). Students' engagement in school is a multidimensional construct that includes several dimensions, namely, emotional, behavioural and cognitive.

Cognitive Engagement: It can be understood as a student's psychological importance in their own knowledge. At the point When a student is cognitively engaged, they believe what they are doing, focus on achieving goals, challenge themselves in their work, and make you aware of their unhappiness.

Behavioural Engagement: refers to students' involvement in classroom activities and in learning. This consists of holding fast to behaviour rules, leaving to exercises as necessary and reaching at classes on time.

Emotional Engagement: refers to the connections among students and their teachers, schoolmates and school. It is likewise to be entitled 'recognizable proof' with learning and school rehearses. Learners who are occupied in when they consider incorporated into they prepare and consider a passionate security with its teachers, with their school and their companions.

Gutierrez and Tomas (2019) found that school engagement and self-efficacy has direct impact on subjective well-being. Teachers' autonomy had significant direct impact on self-efficacy and school engagement and as a reliable predictor of subjective happiness. Students' academic success was described by the impact of emotional and cognitive engagement and self-efficacy. It also revealed that school engagement and self-efficacy intervened the impact of academic success and teachers' autonomy support.

Maamin, Maat and Iksan (2022) conducted a study on 227 schools. This study conducts a survey to determine the influence of student engagement on mathematical achievement. Stratified random sampling was employed to select secondary school students. questionnaires method has been used to collect the data. These findings suggest that students' focus and dedication during mathematics instruction can enhance their mathematical performance. High academic achievement is attained by students who pay attention and are diligent in their study habits, whereas low academic achievement is attained by those who do not. In order to achieve, diligent pupils put forth effort to solve mathematical puzzles. According to this study, there is a strong correlation between student engagement and mathematical proficiency.

MOTIVATIONAL BELIEFS

Motivation is derived from **Latin** word **Movere** which mean “**to move**”. Motivation is defined as an internal condition that motivates us to take certain acts, pushes us in certain ways, and compels us to keep doing those actions (Üür, 2010; Ormrod, 2016). Students that are driven to learn exhibit the following behaviors: participate in class, repeat facts, relate to their prior knowledge, and ask questions. This is because all of their needs and expectations have been met. In short, these students are eager to learn. A student's reactions towards learning lead him to success. It is not possible to talk about success for individuals who are not in action (Schunk, 2009). The urge of satisfying the needs of the individual is the principal driver of motivation.

In addition, many concepts, such as interest, values, attitude and desire of the individual towards an action, affect the process of motivation as well (Akpur,2015). As a result, motivation has a complex structure rather than a straightforward one. In this regard, each individual may have a different amount of motivation. Deci and Ryan (2002) looked at three types of motivation that impact performance:

(i). **Intrinsic Motivation:** If the factors that direct the individual to a certain behaviour comes from his own inner world, in a manner that is independent of the drives outside of the individual, this is intrinsic motivation (Ural,2009). The individual's interest, curiosity, and needs are the primary sources of intrinsic motivation. Students are naturally rewarded for actions carried out of intrinsic motivation and that come from these sources.

(ii). **Extrinsic Motivation:** If the drive of the individual's behaviour is independent of him, in other words if it lies in his environment, then this is extrinsic motivation. The behaviours which originate from outside sources, like prizes, punishment, and social support, are behaviours which are linked with the result of the individual's action (Erdoğan,2013).

(iii). **Amotivation:** People lose motivation and become unmotivated if they are unable to make the connection between their acts and the outcomes of those actions (Reeve, 2014).

Mirhosseini, Lavasani and Hejazi (2018) studied the influence on motivation and academic self-efficacy among students of self-regulated learning skills. Harter's educational motivation questionnaire and academic self-efficacy questionnaire were administered. One factor covariance analysis depicted that motivation and academic self-efficacy had significant effect of self-regulated learning skills.

Mustamiah and Widanti (2020) conducted a study on 226 pupils from three private junior high schools in Surabaya's Bulak subdistrict out of a total enrollment of 540 kids. The aim of this research is to determine the effect of achievement motivation towards student engagement mainly in coastal area of Surabaya. This research uses quantitative approach with regression design. The result of this research also found out believe there is a link between the desire to learn and student engagement. This is in line with Wormington, Corpus and Anderson (2011) who argued that learning motivation is related to academic performance and academic engagement. That is, if students are encouraged to do the learning, then the students will have willingness to participate in many activities as parts of the school programs.

SOCIAL SUPPORT

Shumaker and Brownell (1984) define social support as 'an exchange of resources between at least two parties that is viewed as designed to improve the recipient's well-being by either the supplier or the recipient.

According to Lakey and Cohen (2000), there are two types of social support: received social support, which refers to how frequently people offer you encouragement and comfort, and perceived social support, which refers to how much social assistance you would have at your disposal if you needed it. Social Support is present in classes where the teacher encourages students by conveying high expectations from them. These high expectations may reinforce risk taking in completing challenging academic work. Mutual respect among all the members of a group expresses the existence of social support in the classroom. Mutual respect refers to how pupils who are less proficient in a subject are handled. continue to encourage them and make their presence valued. If disagreement or conflict develops in the classroom, The instructor supports the students in finding a solution that benefits all parties involved. A lack of social support is evident when a teacher or students' behavior, statements, or actions discourage effort, participation, and risks taking to learn or express one's views (Laxman, 2001). Student perceptions of teacher support have been associated with greater feelings of school belonging (e.g., Ma, 2003), and greater school/academic engagement and motivation, as well as better academic performance (e.g., Birch & Ladd, 1998).

Teachers are an essential source of support for pupils in addition to families and peers. Teachers assist students in developing their personalities and in becoming self-sufficient adults (Sayar, 2006).

According to Abdullah and Singh (2019), social support had a big impact on how engaged secondary school pupils were in their studies. Social support plays an essential position in determining student engagement. Students' who receives support from parents, teachers and other spouses are more engaged in their studies. It implies that social support can play a significant role in predicting student engagement. so, it can be revealed that social support had significant impact on student engagement.

Ahola, Soini, Pietarinen and Pyhalto (2021) revealed that adolescent pupils experience relatively strong support from inside school (teachers and peers), as well as home. especially the experienced support from peers was rated quite high. Moreover, According to our findings, social support from teachers and parents is a robust predictor of experienced peer support. The

association between support from instructors and peers, or the actors in the school context, is also the strongest.

RATIONAL OF THE PROBLEM

An analysis of the review of related literature suggest that social support makes inspiration for students to accomplish support may originate from guardians motivating each other to do well in school, and even neighbours and community privileges offering assistance and support to students. It is clear from above discussion that a number of researchers are conducted to explore the role of motivational beliefs on student engagement and to explore role of social support on student engagement. study revealed that motivational beliefs and social support effect student engagement in school. But there is no research, which explore the role of social support and motivational beliefs jointly on the student engagement among senior secondary school students.

HYPOTHESES

1. There exists no significant difference in student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support among secondary school students with respect to gender.
2. There exists no significant difference in student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support among secondary school students with respect to age.

SAMPLING PROCEDURE

A Sample of 200 Students from Government Senior Secondary Schools of Amritsar (Both Male and Female) was selected for the present study. Sample has been Selected From 3 Government Senior Secondary Schools of Amritsar district. The Sample of Schools has been Selected Randomly from Area of Amritsar.

RESEARCH DESIGN OF THE STUDY

The Present Study included in the Descriptive Study as it intends to study Student Engagement, Motivational Beliefs and Social Support among Secondary Schools Students: Difference in gender and age.

TOOLS USED IN THE STUDY

The following tools have been administered on the subjects in study:

TOOL 1 Student Engagement Scale by Kamat, Vasudha and Falleiro, Sameena (2013).

TOOL 2 Motivational beliefs scale by Singh and Kavita (2019).

TOOL 3 Social Support Scale by Dull and Godara (2016).

SATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

- 1 Descriptive statistics techniques such as mean, standard deviation was used to see the nature of distribution of the scores.
- 2 t-test was applied to determine the significant difference between groups with respect to gender.
- 3 One-way ANOVA was applied to determine the significant difference between the groups with respect to age.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE - 1 SIGNIFICANCE OF DIFFERENCE IN STUDENT ENGAGEMENT, MOTIVATIONAL BELIEFS, AND SOCIAL SUPPORT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

	GENDER	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Std. Error Difference	t-value	P value
STUDENT ENGAGEMENT	MALE	99	39.98	5.351	.538	.732	2.666	.008
	FEMALE	101	41.93	4.995	.497			
MOTIVATIONAL BELIEFS	MALE	99	104.08	9.488	.954	1.453	1.512	.132
	FEMALE	101	106.28	10.988	1.093			
SOCIAL SUPPORT	MALE	99	90.17	8.524	.857	1.260	2.606	.010
	FEMALE	101	93.46	9.275	.923			

Hypothesis was framed to examine the difference in student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support among secondary school students with respect to gender.

To test the hypothesis, t-test was applied to determine the significant difference in student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support among secondary school students with respect to gender.

The result of this analysis has been reported in table 1.

The table 1. reveals that calculated p-value .008 and .010 was found to be less than at 0.05 level of significance. So, it reveals that there is a significant difference in student engagement and social support among secondary school students with respect to gender. Further the table 1. reveals that calculated p-value .132 was found to be greater than at 0.05 level of significance.

So, it reveals that there was no significant difference in motivational beliefs among secondary school students with respect to gender.

As shown in the table 1. The mean of adolescent males is 39.98,104.08 and 90.17 and that of females is 41.93,106.28 and 93.46. the means of two groups suggests that adolescent females have better student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support as compared to adolescent male students.

The null hypothesis 1. (a) “There exists no significant difference in student engagement among secondary school students with respect to gender,” has been rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

The null hypothesis 1. (b) “There exists no significant difference in motivational beliefs among secondary school students with respect to gender” was not rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

The null hypothesis 1. (c) “There exists no significant difference in social support among secondary school students with respect to gender,” has been rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

TABLE 2 p-VALUE OF DIFFERENT DIMENSIONS OF STUDENT ENGAGEMENT SCORES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Std.Error difference	t-value	p-value
Cognitive	Male	99	13.20	2.886	.290	.397	1.509	.133
	Female	101	13.80	2.735	.272			
Affective	Male	99	13.98	2.684	.270	.399	.622	.535
	Female	101	14.23	2.946	.293			
Behavioral	Male	99	12.90	2.517	.253	.355	2.822	.005
	Female	101	13.90	2.504	.249			

The table 2 reveals that individually t-test was applied to the different dimensions (cognitive, Affective and behavioral) of student engagement. From the above table 2 it can be seen that significant difference was found in behavioral dimension of student engagement at 0.05 level of significance. An examination of the means of two group suggest that female students have better behavioral dimension as compared to male students.

TABLE 3 p-VALUE OF DIFFERENT DIMENSIONS OF SOCIAL SUPPORT SCORES OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO GENDER

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	Std.deviation	Std. error mean	Std. error difference	t-value	p-value																																						
Family support	Male	99	23.13	2.514	.253	.369	2.191	.030																																						
	Female	101	23.94	2.705	.269				Teacher support	Male	99	22.62	2.736	.275	.366	2.723	.007	Female	101	23.61	2.441	.243	Friends peer support	Male	99	22.18	2.749	.276	.383	2.651	.009	Female	101	23.20	2.672	.266	Online support	Male	99	22.24	3.172	.319	.431	2.263	.025	Female
Teacher support	Male	99	22.62	2.736	.275	.366	2.723	.007																																						
	Female	101	23.61	2.441	.243				Friends peer support	Male	99	22.18	2.749	.276	.383	2.651	.009	Female	101	23.20	2.672	.266	Online support	Male	99	22.24	3.172	.319	.431	2.263	.025	Female	101	23.22	2.921	.291										
Friends peer support	Male	99	22.18	2.749	.276	.383	2.651	.009																																						
	Female	101	23.20	2.672	.266				Online support	Male	99	22.24	3.172	.319	.431	2.263	.025	Female	101	23.22	2.921	.291																								
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The table 3 reveals that individually t-test was applied to the different dimensions (Family support, Teacher support, Friends peer Support and online Support) of Social Support. from the above table 3 it reveals that a significant difference was found in family support, teacher support, friends peer support and online support of social support at 0.05 level of significance. Female students have higher Family, teacher, friends, peer and online support than male students.

It was concluded that female students have higher student engagement than male students and female and male students have do not differ on motivational beliefs and further it was concluded that female students have higher social support than males students. Study reveals that females' students have better behavioral dimension as compared to male students. it was concluded that females students have higher family, teacher, friends, peer and online support than male students.

TABLE 4 SIGNIFICANCE OF DIFFERENCE IN STUDENT ENGAGEMENT, MOTIVATIONAL BELIEFS AND SOCIAL SUPPORT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO AGE.

	Age (14,15,16)	N	Mean	Std.deviation
Student	14	82	39.51	4.780
Engagement	15	94	41.44	5.303
Total	16	24	44.08	5.098

	Total	200	40.97	5.253
Motivational Beliefs Total	14	82	103.51	10.135
	15	94	106.16	10.067
	16	24	107.13	11.388
	Total	200	105.19	10.306
Social Support Total	14	82	92.15	9.303
	15	94	92.51	8.610
	16	24	88.08	9.254
	Total	200	91.83	9.040

In order to analysis the variance in student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support the obtained scores are subjected to ANOVA and the result have been presented as given in table 5

TABLE 5

	Source of variance	df	Sum of squares	Mean square	f-value	significance
Student Engagement Total	Between groups	2	427.317	213.658	8.313	.000
	Within groups	197	5063.438	25.703		
	Total	199	5490.755		Significance	
Motivational Beliefs Total	Between groups	2	409.061	204.530	1.944	.146
	Within groups	197	20727.719	105.217		
	Total	199	21136.780		Insignificance	
Social Support Total	Between groups	2	388.653	194.327	2.412	.092
	Within groups	197	15873.567	80.576		
	Total	199	16262.220		Insignificance	

The table 5 reveals that the F-value for the difference between students engagement with respect to their age came out to be 8.313 which is significant at both level. And further it reveals

that the f-value for the difference between motivational beliefs and social support with respect to their age came out to be 1.944 and 2.412 which is insignificant at both levels.

Hence, the hypothesis 2(a) “there exists no significant difference in student engagement among secondary school students with respect to age” has been rejected. Statistically significant mean difference was found in scores of student engagement of secondary school students with respect to age group. the mean score of age group 16 years students was highest followed by 15 years and 14 years of students.

Hence, the hypothesis 2(b) “There exists no significant difference in motivational beliefs among secondary schools’ students with respect to age” was not rejected.

Statistically no significant mean difference was found in scores of motivational beliefs of secondary school students with respect to age group. the result reveals that students of different age groups do not differ with respect to motivational beliefs.

Hence the hypothesis 2(c) “There exists no significant difference in social support among secondary school students with respect to age” was not rejected. Statistically insignificant mean difference was found in scores of social support of secondary school students with respect to age.

In order to analysis the variance in student engagement the obtained scores are subjected to ANOVA and the result have been presented as given in table 6

TABLE 6

	Source of variance	Df	Sum of square	Mean square	f- value	Significance
Cognitive	Between groups	2	139.440	69.720	9.521	.000
	Within groups	197	1442.555	7.323		
	Total	199	1581.995			Significance
Affective	Between groups	2	73.913	36.956	4.844	.009
	Within groups	197	1502.882	7.629		
	Total	199	1576.795			Significance
Behavioral	Between groups	2	10.595	5.298	.811	.446
	Within groups	197	1287.600	6.536		
	Total	199	1298.195			Insignificance

Student engagement total	Between groups	2	427.317	213.658	8.313	.000 Significance
	Within groups	197	5063.438	25.703		
	Total	199	5490.755			

The table 6 reveals that F-value for the difference between students engagement with respect to cognitive, affective and behavioral level which is significant at cognitive and affective level. The result reveals that students of different age group differ with respect to cognitive and affective domains of student engagement.

DISCUSSION

The main objective of the study was to understand the significance of difference in student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support among secondary school students with respect to gender and significance difference in student engagement, motivational beliefs and social support among secondary school students with respect to age. In this study descriptive statistics techniques such as mean, standard deviation was used to see the nature of distribution of the scores. T-test was applied to determine the significant difference between groups with respect to gender. One- way ANOVA was applied to determine the significant difference between the groups with respect to age. The findings of the study indicated that female students have higher student engagement than male students and female and male students have do not differ on motivational beliefs and it was found that female students have higher social support than males students. study reveals that females students have better behavioral dimension as compared to male students. it was found that females students have higher family, teacher, friends, peer and online support than male students. Further the results revealed that students of different age groups differ with respect to cognitive and affective domains of student engagement. These results were consistent with previous studies Ferrel (2012) conducted a study to ascertain that there would be significant connections between motivational features of the student engagement and social classroom environment. Yassin and Dzulkifli (2009) revealed that those students who have higher social support have a tendency to achieve better in their academics than the learners who have a lower level of social support. Abdullah and Singh (2019) conducted a study on 700 senior secondary school students Jammu and Kashmir. It implies that social support can play a significant role in predicting student engagement. So it can be revealed that social support had significant impact on student engagement.

CONCLUSION

The study presented the following conclusion:

- The present study revealed that the females' students have higher student engagement than male adolescent students. Further it was revealed that female's students were better behavioural dimension of students' engagement than males' students.
- It was found that students of 16 years age group exhibited better student engagement followed by 15 and 14 years of students. Further the present study revealed that students of different age group differ with respect to cognitive and affective domain of student engagement.
- The present study revealed that males and female's students do not differ with respect to motivational beliefs.
- The present study found that students of different age group do not differ with respect to motivational beliefs.
- It was found that the females have higher social support than male students. There was a significance different found between different dimensions (family support, teacher support, friends peer support and online support) of social support.
- The present study revealed that students of different age groups do not differ with respect to social support.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah, B. & Singh, K. (2019). Academic performance of senior secondary school students in relation to their self-efficacy and social support. *American International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Social Science*, 26(1), 09-12.
- Ahola, R., Soini, T., Pietarinen, J., & Pyhalto, K. (2021). Social support experiences by pupils in Finnish secondary school. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*. 26(1), 471-486.

- Akpur, U. (2015). *The Relationship Pattern between English Prep School Students' Academic Achievement and their Academic Motivation, Anxiety and Attitudes*. (Unpublished Master Dissertation). Yildiz Teknik University, Istanbul.
- Birch, S. & Ladd, G.W. (1998). Children's interpersonal behaviors and the teacher-child relationship. *Developmental Psychology*, 34, 934-946.
- Bomia, L., Beluzo, L., Demeester, D., Elander, K., Johnson, M., & Sheldon, B. (1997). *The Impact of Teaching Strategies on Intrinsic Motivation*. Champaign, IL: ERIC Clearinghouse on Elementary and Early Childhood Education.
- Cogur, H.C. (2010). *The Usage of Motivation tools in Project Management and its Implication in the Turkish Construction Sector*. (Unpublished master's thesis). Cukurova university, Adana.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R.M. (2002). *Handbook of Self Determination Research*. Rochester, NY: University of Rochester press.
- Erdogan, B. (2013). The effect of adaptive learning management system on student's Satisfaction, motivation and achievement in online learning (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation). Ankara University, Ankara.
- Ersoy-Kart, M. & Guldu, O. (2008). Self -determination. Scale: the adaptation study. *Ankara University Journal of Faculty of Educational Sciences*, 41(2): 187-207.
- Gallup, L. L. C. (2013). *State of the American Workplace Employee Engagement Insights for US Business Leaders*. Retrieved from Washington, DC. <http://www.gallup.com>.
- games to academic achievement and motivation (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation). Anadolu University, Eskisehir.
- Garavandi, AH., Damir, H. & Kar, RZ. (2015). Study the simple and multiple relationship between social support, job motivation and job satisfaction among high school female teachers in Baghmalek city. *Visi Journal Akademik*, 8: 64-67.
- Gutierrez, M., & Tomas, J. M. (2019). The role of perceived autonomy support in predicting university students' academic success mediated by academic self- efficacy and school engagement. *Educational Psychology*, 39(6), 729-748.
- Lakey, B., & Cohen, S.(2000). Social support theory and measurement. In S. Cohen, L.G.underwood, & B.H. Gottlieb (Eds.), *Social Support Measurement and Intervention (pp. 29-52)*. New York: Oxford University Press.

- Laxman, D. (2010). Impact of academic motivation and perceptions of classroom climate on academic achievement of secondary school students in north coastal Andhra region. (Unpublished Ph.D Dissertation) Andhra university, pradesh, India.
- Lin, T. (2012). *Student Engagement and Motivation in the Foreign Language Classroom*. (Unpublished doctoral thesis). United States: Washington State University.
- Ma, X. (2003). Sense of belonging to school: can schools make a difference? *The Journal of Educational Research*, 96(6), 340-349.
- Maamin, M., Mistima Maat, S., & Iksan, Z. (2022). The influence of student engagement on mathematical achievement among secondary school students. <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/mathematics> , 1-14.
- Middleton, J. A. & Spanias, P. A. (1999). Motivation for achievement in mathematics: findings, generalization and criticism of the research. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 30(1), 65-88.
- Mirhosseini, F.S., Lavasani, M.G., & Hejazi, E. (2018). The effectiveness of self-regulation learning skill on motivational and academic variable among students. *World Family Medicines*, 16(5), 68-75. DOI:10.5742/MEWFM.2018.93385.
- Mustamiah, D. & Widanti, N. (2020). Learning motivation as predictor of student engagement in private 21 n kara high schools students. *In Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Psychology in Health, Educational, Social, and Organizational Settings (ICO-HESOS 2018)- Improving Mental Health and Harmony in Global Community*, 486-493.
- Ormrod, J.E. (2015). *Ogrenme Psikolojisi*. (Cev. M. Baloglu). ankara:nobel yayilik.
- Reeve, J. (2014). *Understanding Motivation and Emotion*. New York, United States of America:Wiley.
- Russell, V. J., Ainley, M., & Frydenberg, E. (2005). Student motivation and engagement. *Schooling Issues Digest*. Australian Government, Department of Education, Science and Training.
- Sayar, M. (2006). A Longitudinal study of the relationship between perceived social support and psychological well-being of adolescent from low socioeconomic status. *Yukse Lisans Tezi*. Bogazici University, Institute of Social Sciences.
- Schlechty, P.C. (2001). *Shaking up The Schoolhouse*. San Fransisco, USA: Jossey-Bass Publishers.

- Schunk, D.H. (2009). Learning theories: An educational Perspective .*Ankara: Nobel*.
- Shumaker, S.A. & Brownell, A. (1984). Towards a theory of social support : Closing conceptual gaps, *Journal of Social Issues*, 40(4), 11-36(cited by: Redman, T., 2005, The consequences of Perceived Age Discrimination Amongst Older Police Officers: Is Social Support a Buffer?, WP-100, ISSN:1749-3641).
- Shumaker, S.A. & Brownell, A. (1984). Towards a theory of social support : Closing conceptual gaps, *Journal of Social Issues*, 40(4), 11-36(cited by: Redman, T., 2005, The consequences of Perceived Age Discrimination Amongst Older Police Officers: Is Social Support a Buffer?, WP-100, ISSN:1749-3641).
- Sternberg, R. J. (2005). Intelligence, competence and expertise. In E. Andrew & D, Carol (Eds.), *Hand Book of Competence and Motivation*. New York. USA: The Guilford Press.
- Ural, M.N. (2009). The effect of entertaining and motivational properties of educational games to academic achievement and motivation (Unpublished Doctoral dissertation). Anadolu University, Eskisehir.